

Reframing AI-Centered Narratives: An Analysis of Google's Notebook LM Podcast Feature

Author: Christian Ortiz

Institution: Mod Atlas Media, Justice AI Research Institute

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Abstract

This study critically examines an AI-generated podcast produced by Google's Notebook LM software, revealing the systemic centering of white perspectives, even when engaging with content focused on racial injustice. By analyzing the podcast generated from an article about Grace Gee's "Bubbling Up" project, we identify how AI systems perpetuate dominant cultural narratives, often sidelining the very communities the content seeks to represent. This research demonstrates the importance of integrating broader epistemic frameworks into AI to foster inclusive, equitable representation. We argue that only by addressing the inherent biases within AI design can these technologies contribute meaningfully to social justice.

Introduction

AI technologies are becoming deeply embedded in media production, often shaping conversations in ways that reflect existing power structures. While such technologies are often presented as objective tools, they frequently reinforce the perspectives and experiences of dominant groups. This study focuses on a podcast generated by Google's Notebook LM, which, when fed an article on Grace Gee's "Bubbling Up" project, produced a conversation that placed white experiences at the forefront of a discussion on racial justice. The podcast reflects broader patterns in which marginalized voices are obscured, even when discussing issues directly relevant to them.

Through this case study, we seek to explore how AI systems can subtly perpetuate dominance by normalizing certain perspectives while marginalizing others. Our analysis proposes a pathway for integrating more diverse perspectives into AI-generated content, ultimately leading to richer, more inclusive narratives.

Methodology

This study employs a qualitative case study approach, analyzing the AI-generated podcast as both a product of its algorithm and a reflection of the broader social context in which AI operates. The input document—a written article on Grace Gee's "Bubbling Up" project, which addresses racial injustice and community healing—was used to generate a nine-minute podcast episode. We then analyzed the resulting conversation through a lens that considers the structural biases embedded in AI design and output.

The key analytical questions included:

1. **Representation and Voice:** Who does the AI select as primary voices, and how do these choices reflect broader societal patterns of inclusion and exclusion?
 2. **Narrative Focus:** What themes are emphasized in the AI's output, and how do these reflect or obscure the original intent of the input material?
 3. **Systems of Power:** How does the AI reinforce or challenge existing power dynamics through its framing of the subject matter?
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Findings

AI's Selection of Interlocutors

The podcast featured two white speakers—a man and a woman—who engaged in a conversation about racial injustice, despite the subject matter being focused on the lived experiences of marginalized communities. This choice mirrors a larger trend where AI systems prioritize voices from dominant social groups, reinforcing the visibility of those already in positions of power. In this case, the AI chose to foreground the perspectives of individuals who are least likely to be directly affected by racial injustice, thereby shifting the narrative away from the communities most impacted by the issue.

The Framing of Racial Injustice

Rather than centering the voices of those whose stories were shared in the "Bubbling Up" project, the podcast framed the issue of racial injustice through the lens of white empathy and responsibility. The speakers emphasized how white participants in the art exhibit were encouraged to engage in "actionable allyship," shifting the focus from the structural causes of racial injustice to the personal journey of white individuals. This re-centering of the narrative

positions white people as the agents of change, subtly reinforcing the idea that progress hinges on their actions rather than the empowerment of marginalized communities.

Obscured Systemic Context

Although the original article highlighted the historical and structural forces behind racial injustice, the AI's framing largely stripped away this context, focusing instead on individual stories and emotional responses. This reductionist approach downplays the complexity of systemic issues, making it harder to grasp the full scope of the project's intent. In doing so, the AI perpetuates a narrative that focuses on surface-level engagement, rather than a deeper understanding of the root causes of injustice.

Discussion: Expanding the Narrative Space

The findings from this case study highlight the ways in which AI systems are predisposed to reinforce dominant narratives, even when engaging with content that seeks to challenge them. While the "Bubbling Up" project was designed to confront and expose the realities of racial injustice, the AI system repackaged this content in a way that maintained the status quo, centering the experiences of those least affected by the issue.

To foster more equitable and inclusive AI-generated content, it is crucial to incorporate design principles that account for the diversity of perspectives and experiences in the input material. This requires a shift in how AI systems are trained and developed, ensuring that they are capable of representing the full spectrum of human experiences, rather than defaulting to the voices of those in power. Integrating epistemic diversity into AI models would allow for more nuanced outputs that reflect a broader range of perspectives, particularly those from communities historically marginalized in media and technology.

Moving Toward Inclusive AI

One way to address these issues is to broaden the sources of data used to train AI systems, ensuring that they are exposed to a wider range of perspectives from different cultural, social, and historical contexts. Additionally, embedding principles of equity into the design and evaluation of AI systems can help mitigate the biases that lead to the centering of dominant narratives. By doing so, AI can be a tool that amplifies marginalized voices rather than one that silences them.

Conclusion

This case study demonstrates the importance of critically evaluating the ways in which AI systems interact with and reproduce cultural narratives. Without deliberate efforts to diversify the voices and perspectives represented in AI-generated media, these systems will continue to reinforce the experiences of dominant social groups, even in contexts explicitly aimed at addressing injustice. Through intentional design and evaluation, AI has the potential to play a transformative role in fostering more inclusive and equitable media landscapes.

The implications of this research extend beyond the specific case of Google's Notebook LM to broader conversations about the role of AI in society. As AI continues to shape how stories are told and whose voices are heard, it is essential that we push for systems that do not simply mirror existing inequalities, but actively work to dismantle them.

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Appendix A: Transcript of the AI-Generated Podcast from Google's Notebook LM

Below is the verbatim transcript of the AI-generated podcast episode produced by Google's Notebook LM in response to an uploaded article about Grace Gee's "Bubbling Up" project. This transcript serves as primary evidence for the analysis conducted in the main body of the study, offering readers the opportunity to directly engage with the AI's output.

Podcast Title: Bubbling Up: Art, Racial Justice, and AI

Duration: 9 minutes 8 seconds

Speakers: AI-generated male speaker (M) and AI-generated female speaker (F)

[Introduction]

M: Ever imagine art could, like, actually heal a community? And we're doing this deep dive on "Bubbling Up." It's a project, right? And it mixes storytelling, racial justice, even AI. Kind of wild, right?

F: Picture this: delicate bubbles just hanging in a gallery, each one holding someone's real experience with racial injustice. Wow. But here's the thing—these stories are going up in places that are mostly white. Makes you think, huh? Can art really bridge those divides, especially around racial injustice? And where does AI even fit in? Let's find out.

[Segment 1: Bubbling Up and the Power of Storytelling]

M: What grabs me about "Bubbling Up" is how ambitious it is. This isn't just a "be aware" kind of project. It's pushing for actual change.

F: Right, right. It's definitely not your average art show. Not at all. We're going off some excerpts from this article about it. So, imagine walking into a gallery—soft light, but instead of paintings, it's these shimmery bubbles everywhere. Each one's got a story inside, someone's own experience with racial injustice. They submitted it to the project.

M: And the artist, Grace Gee—her studio is called Healing Grace Studio—they're putting these installations in mostly white spaces on purpose. What do you think's up with that?

F: I think it's about forcing a reckoning. That moment when people who might never encounter these stories, it's right there in their face. You can't look away. "Bubbling Up" makes racial injustice impossible to ignore. They're like holding up a mirror to society.

[Segment 2: The Role of AI in Racial Justice]

M: Exactly. But here's where it gets really interesting—they've added in artificial intelligence.

F: Oh, wow. AI, really?

M: Yeah, it's called Justice AI, made by this guy Christian Ortiz. Now, AI can be kind of techie, so bear with me. Imagine, instead of just reading the story alone, Justice AI gives you background—historical facts, stats, maybe even laws connected to that experience. So you're not just getting the one story, you're getting the whole—

F: A context, yeah. Got it. It makes it hit different, right? It has to.

M: Exactly. And they've even got these QR codes, the article mentions, right there in the exhibit. You scan one with your phone, bam. You're not just seeing art, you're getting this whole curated layer of info. Makes you think harder about it all. It's making the invisible visible.

[Segment 3: Encouraging Action and Allyship]

F: "Bubbling Up" uses Justice AI to show you the stuff that's usually hidden—those systemic factors behind the individual stories.

M: Exactly. And it makes you wonder, like, if WE had that kind of context in our everyday lives, would we see the world differently? Would we notice those smaller things, those little injustices we usually miss?

F: This project isn't just about taking in information. It's about sparking conversation.

M: Totally. And it's really effective at getting white participants to—well, the article calls it "actionable allyship."

F: Actionable allyship. OK, let's break that down. That's a powerful phrase. What's it mean in this situation, with this project?

M: I think it means saying, "Yeah, this is messed up" isn't enough. "Bubbling Up" is asking white people: What are you going to do about it? It's about turning empathy into action.

[Segment 4: Creating a Shared Responsibility]

F: 100%. And they actually encourage that, right there in the exhibit. Imagine you read a story, you're feeling all those emotions. But then you get to write down your reaction, your thoughts, questions—maybe even what you're going to do about it. And then those responses, they become part of the art, too, right alongside the original story.

M: Wow. So, it's a conversation then, back and forth.

F: Exactly. By including those responses, they're showing that dealing with racial injustice—it's on all of us. It's a shared responsibility.

M: Which isn't something you see every day at an art show. That call to action, especially with such a heavy topic, is pretty incredible.

[Conclusion: Art, Tech, and Change]

F: And that's where this mix of art and cutting-edge tech, like Justice AI, is so smart. It's not just throwing information at you, it's connecting you to the bigger picture—how these individual stories fit into the larger systems we don't always see.

M: It makes you realize that these aren't just isolated experiences—they're part of something much bigger, much deeper. It's about understanding that these individual stories connect to this broader reality of racial injustice.

F: Yeah, and that understanding, it's what gives you power to act. You go from just feeling bad to actually knowing what to do about it. It's hopeful, in a way. "Bubbling Up" shows us that change is possible—real change—if we're willing to face the hard truths.

M: Exactly. It's amazing how something as light as a bubble can hold so much weight, isn't it?

F: Totally. And in the end, it's about more than just seeing the art—it's about engaging with it, letting it change you. And if that happens, who knows what kind of world we can create?

[Outro]

M: Thanks for joining us for this deep dive into Grace Gee's "Bubbling Up." If you're interested, check out Healing Grace Studio online to read more stories and see the project in action.

F: And most importantly, think about what you can do, right where you are, to make things better. Because, as we've said, it's on all of us.

M: Until next time, keep those conversations going and keep on digging deeper.